

Structure Based Drug Designing and Molecular Docking Studies of Monosubstituted 1-Cyano-2-methyl-3-([2-(5-methyl-1H-imidazol-4-yl)ethyl]sulfanyl)methyl)guanidine (Cimetidine) with Cytochrome P450 (CYP450) Enzyme

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Abstract

1-cyano-2-methyl-3-([2-(5-methyl-1H-imidazol-4-yl)ethyl]sulfanyl)methyl)guanidine (cimetidine) is a drug that helps in the reduction of stomach acidity, pepsin output reduction and promotion of ulcer healing. We carried out molecular docking for six analogous structurally diverse 1-cyano-2-methyl-3-([2-(5-methyl-1H-imidazol-4-yl)ethyl]sulfanyl)methyl)guanidine (cimetidine) with cytochrome P450 1A2 using Patchdock and Firedock softwares. Extensive structure activity relationship studies was carried out with the substituted derivatives and compared with the non-substituted. These molecules were designed by substituting different chemical groups on position 17 of cimetidine. The scoring function (empirical binding free energy) was used to estimate the free binding energy of the protein-ligand complex. The binding energy of cimetidine was -30.96 kcal/mol. The free binding energies of COOH, COCH₃, NO₂, CF₃ and CONH₂ analogues were -33.12, -31.67, -34.67, -34.73 and -36.58 Kcal/mol respectively. All the monosubstituted analogues showed lower values than the non substituted cimetidine. These lower values indicate that they inhibit CYP450 functional activity. These results suggest that the new inhibitors may cause hepatotoxicity. Synthesis and pre-clinical studies of these monosubstituted derivatives with cytochrome P₄₅₀ 1A2 receptors is recommended in order to confirm their hepatotoxicity.

Keywords: Cimetidine, Docking, Cytochrome P450, Binding affinities, Scoring function.

INTRODUCTION

Cimetidine, a [potent](#) CYP450 [enzyme inhibitor](#). It helps in the reduction of stomach acidity, pepsin output reduction and promotion of ulcer healing (Elks, 2014; IDD, 2000, Morton *et al.*, 2015; Yusuf, 2007). It is mainly used in the treatment of heartburn, peptic ulcer, abomasal and duodenal ulcers, drug induced erosive gastritis, duodenal gastric reflux and oesophageal reflux healing (Elks, 2014; Morton *et al.*, 2015; Yusuf, 2007; Burchum and Rosenthal, 2014). The use of cimetidine has been decreased with the development of other longer acting H₂ receptor antagonists with fewer adverse effects such as famotidine and ranitidine. The monosubstituted derivative of cimetidine could have an improvement with a wider spectrum of activity.

The monosubstituted derivative of cimetidine could also reduce the side effects of cimetidine such as, constipation, rashes, muscle pain at the site of injection, fatigue, dizziness and mental confusion (Ritter *et al.*, 2008). The changes in the substituent of cimetidine may be very safe in [overdose](#), producing no [symptoms](#) even at high overdoses (Dart, 2004). Cimetidine is metabolized through S-oxygenation by [flavin-containing monooxygenases](#), specifically [FMO1](#) and [FMO3](#) (Cashman, 2000). Cimetidine is a [potent](#) but not a universal inhibitor of CYP450 [enzyme](#) (Dart, 2004; Lemke and Williams, 2008) but it inhibits a broad array of CYP450 [isoforms](#), including [CYP1A2](#), [CYP2C9](#), [CYP2C19](#), [CYP2D6](#), [CYP2E1](#), and [CYP3A4](#) (Dart, 2004; Lemke and Williams, 2008; Karalliedde *et al.*, 2010) and it is said to be most potent in inhibiting CYP1A2, CYP2D6, and CYP3A4 (Priskorn *et al.*, 1997) of which it is described as a moderate inhibitor (Elks, 2014), and this is notable as these three [isoenzymes](#) are involved in the majority of CYP450-mediated drug [biotransformations](#) (Martínez *et al.*, 1999). As such, cimetidine has the potential for a large number of [drug interactions](#) (Dart, 2004; Lemke and Williams, 2008; Karalliedde *et al.*, 2010). CYP450 [enzymes](#) are involved in the elimination of xenobiotic detoxification of harmful carcinogenic substances. Cytochrome P450 1A2 receptors are mainly expressed in the human liver and participate in the oxidation of drugs.

Modern approaches to finding new drugs for therapeutics in man and animals are increasingly based on 3-dimensional information about receptors. An effective way to predict the binding structure of a substrate in its receptor is docking simulation, which has been successfully used in many applications (Lorey *et al.*, 2001; Dixon and Blaney, 1998). Docking procedures basically aim to identify the correct conformation of ligands in the binding pocket of a protein and to predict the affinity between the ligand and the protein. In other words, it describes a process by which two molecules fit together in a 3-dimensional space (Dipankar *et al.*, 2007). Though still in use cimetidine is no longer among the more widely used H₂- receptor antagonist. Therefore the aim of this research is to determine the substituents that will reduce the inhibition of CYP450 [enzyme](#) and recommend these monosubstituted derivatives for synthesis and pre-clinical studies. The structural formula of cimetidine is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Cimetidine structural formula

MATERIAL AND METHODS

a- Protein preparation

The three dimensional structure of Cytochrome P450 receptor was obtained from the Protein Data Bank, PDB ID – 2HI4 (Figure 2). The protein structure was subjected to a refinement protocol using Molegro Molecular Viewer (Molegro Molecular Viewer, 2012).

b-Designing of structural analogs of Cimetidine

The structure of cimetidine (Figure 1) was drawn with ACD/ChemSketch software (Advanced Chemistry Development, 2008). The structural analogues of cimetidine were developed with structural modifications with different substituents. The methyl group at 17 position of cimetidine was replaced with COOH, COCH₃, NO₂, CF₃ and CONH₂ analogues. The structures were built with ACD/ChemSketch software and minimized with Arguslab software (Thompson, 2007).

c-Molecular docking

Molecular docking was performed using Patchdock software (Duhovny *et al.*, 2002). Patchdock is a molecular docking algorithm based on shape complementarity principles. The docking job was refined in Firedock software (Mashiach *et al.*, 2008; Andrusier *et al.*, 2007) and processed with Molegro Molecular Viewer. Lipinski rule of 5 was evaluated using Sanjeevini: a freely accessible web-server for target directed lead molecule discovery (Jayaram *et al.*, 2012).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Estimated free energy of binding (FEB) of cimetidine and its analogues is shown in Table 1. Assessment of drug-likeness of the pre-screened ligand is presented in Table 2. Crystal structure of cytochrome P450 receptor is shown in Figure 2, while the docked cimetidine analogues with cytochrome P450 receptor are presented in Figures 3 – 8. The Hydrogen bonding, electrostatic and steric interactions are depicted in Figures 9 -14.

Tabled 1: Estimated free energy of binding (FEB) of 1-cyano-2-methyl-3-([2-(5-methyl-1H-imidazol-4-yl)ethyl]sulfanyl)methyl)guanidine (cimetidine) and its analogues against cytochrome P450 1A2

Substituent's	Structure	Docking score (Kcal/mol)
CH ₃		-30.96
COOH		-33.12
COCH ₃		-31.67
NO ₂		-34.67
CF ₃		-34.73
CONH ₂		-36.58

Table 2: Assessment of drug-likeness of 1-cyano-2-methyl-3-({[2-(5-methyl-1*H*-imidazol-4-yl)ethyl]sulfanyl)methyl}guanidine (cimetidine) and its analogues

Substituents	Molecular weight	Hydrogen bond donor	Hydrogen bond acceptors:	Lipophilicity LogP	Molar Refractivity
CH ₃	250.000	3.000	5.000	1.632	73.720
COOH	278.000	4.000	7.000	0.715	67.960
COCH ₃	277.000	3.000	6.000	0.827	76.093
NO ₂	282.000	4.000	7.000	0.715	67.960
CF ₃	305.000	3.000	5.000	2.047	73.581
CONH ₂	277.000	4.000	7.000	0.844	76.030

Fig 2: Crystal structure of cytochrome P450 1A2(PDB 2HIA)

Fig 3: Cimetidine docked with cytochrome P450 1A2

Fig 4: COOH analogue of cimetidine docked with cytochrome P450 1A2

Fig 5: COCH₃ analogue of cimetidine docked with cytochrome P450 1A2

Fig 6: NO₂ analogue of cimetidine docked with cytochrome P450 1A2

Fig 7: CF₃ analogue of cimetidine docked with cytochrome P450 1A2

Fig 8: CONH₂ analogue of cimetidine docked with cytochrome P450 1A2

Fig. 9. Hydrogen bonding, electrostatic and steric interactions of CF₃ analogue of cimetidine docked with cytochrome P₄₅₀ 1A2

Fig. 10. Hydrogen bonding, electrostatic and steric interactions of COOH analogue of cimetidine docked with cytochrome P₄₅₀ 1A2

Fig. 11. Hydrogen bonding, electrostatic and steric interactions of CONH₂ analogue of cimetidine docked with cytochrome P₄₅₀ 1A2

Fig. 12. Hydrogen bonding, electrostatic and steric interactions of COCH₃ analogue of cimetidine docked with cytochrome P450 1A2

Fig. 13. Hydrogen bonding, electrostatic and steric interactions of NO₂ analogue of cimetidine docked with cytochrome P450 1A2

Fig. 14. Hydrogen bonding, electrostatic and steric interactions of cimetidine docked with cytochrome P450 1A2

The docking structures of all the compounds showed that they bind in a very similar pattern with the active site of cytochrome P450 receptor, as is evident from the superposition of all the six analogues in Figures 3 - 8. The hydrogen bonding, electrostatic and steric interactions of

cimetidine and its analogues with cytochrome P450 1A2 occurred at Met 453, Met 449, Met 448, Leu 91, Lys 447, Glu 461, Glu 446, Ser 445, Lys 442, Leu 373, Glu 369, Arg 362, Tyr 495, Ser 231, Lys 59, Glu 233, Pro 61, Ser 232, Gly 232, Asn 234, Lys 465 and Arg 95.

The calculated free energy of binding of the six cimetidine analogues was -30.96, -33.12, -31.67, -34.67, -34.73 and -36.58 Kcal/mol (Table 1). This confirms that the structural modification implemented in this study is significantly related to their activity. Also, this proved the reasonability and reliability of the docking results. It can be seen that substitution of NH₂ functional group of cimetidine with CH₃, COOH, COCH₃, NO₂, CF₃ and CONH₂ analogues at positions 17 lead to an increase in the binding affinity of modified analogues which is even more intense than that of cimetidine. The binding energy of cimetidine was -30.96 kcal/mol. These results clearly indicated that before synthesis and biochemical testing of new analogues one can use molecular docking based methods for qualitative assessment of relative binding affinities for speeding up drug discovery process by eliminating less potent compounds from synthesis.

Lipinski rule of 5 (Lipinski, 2004) helps in distinguishing between drug like and non-drug like molecules. It predicts high probability of success or failure due to drug likeness for molecules complying with 2 or more of the following rules: Molecular mass less than 500 Dalton; High lipophilicity (expressed as LogP less than 5); Less than 5 hydrogen bond donors ;Less than 10 hydrogen bond acceptors ;Molar refractivity should be between 40-130. Cimetidine and its modified analogues obeyed the Lipinski rule of 5 (Table 2). These filters help in early preclinical development and could help avoid costly late-stage preclinical and clinical failures.

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